

INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCES IN THE FIELD OF INFORMATION SECURITY AND THEIR SIGNIFICANCE

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ABSTRACT

The analysis of foreign experiences in the field of information security and revealing their philosophical and social essence is of particular importance in today's globalized society. Information flows and digital technologies are reshaping the entire structure of human life, political systems, economic processes, and spiritual values. In this process, the experiences developed by different countries, their strategies and concepts are considered not only as means of technical protection, but also as social phenomena that allow for a philosophical interpretation of humanity's existence in the information space.

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Among foreign experiences, it is noteworthy that European countries interpret information security as a strategic element of national policy. In this approach, information protection is viewed not only as ensuring technological stability but also as preserving the right of society members to think freely and live in an open communication environment. Thus, from the perspective of social philosophy, information security manifests as a process of seeking balance between an individual's communicative freedom and state stability.

In the US experience, information security has become a core element of the national security concept. In this approach, control over information flows serves not only to eliminate external threats but also to strengthen internal social consciousness. In the context of social philosophy, such a model is considered as immunity against the manipulation of human consciousness in global processes. This indicates the need to develop the ability to make conscious choices in the information space during the process of society's self-awareness.

The experience of Eastern countries, particularly Southeast Asia, emphasizes the need to harmonize information security with cultural values. In this approach, information protection

is closely linked to the preservation of national culture and traditional social consciousness. From a philosophical standpoint, this model strengthens humanity's ability to live in the information age without losing its identity.

Therefore, the synthesis of foreign experiences shows that information security is not merely a technological issue, but a factor determining the socio-philosophical existence of society. Through it, individuals strive to preserve their freedom, and the state - its stability. Consequently, analyzing foreign experiences in the field of information security, besides protecting society from external and internal threats, is an important philosophical direction for developing spiritual immunity in global processes, enhancing public consciousness, and strengthening cultural identity.

When analyzing foreign experiences in the field of information security and their significance in the context of social philosophy, they manifest not only as technical mechanisms but also as conceptual principles that strengthen public consciousness and moral immunity. In today's global information space, security policy is not limited to national borders but also encompasses mechanisms of transnational cooperation, institutional dialogue, and social trust. For example, the "General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)" developed in the European Union is considered not only as a data protection system but also as a mechanism for ensuring human rights in the information space. A. Westin emphasizes that "the protection of personal data is a guarantee that a person feels free and independent in the information space"¹.

Foreign experience shows that for an information security policy to be effective, it should not be limited to technological means, but should be aimed at protecting public consciousness from ideological pressures. For example, in the "Cybersecurity Strategy" adopted in the USA, in addition to technical protection, the main emphasis is placed on strengthening citizens' awareness, informing them about hacking, false messages, and manipulations. M. Castells explains this process as "the hierarchy of power in the information society consists not in controlling information flows, but in managing the meaning given to it"². Consequently, in foreign practice, information security is closely related to the philosophical concept of managing public consciousness.

The experience of Eastern countries, in particular Japan, is also noteworthy. In this country, the information security policy, along with protecting technological infrastructure, is aimed at strengthening moral immunity in society, educating young people about information culture, and developing loyalty to national values. K. Nishitani emphasizes that "technology should not alienate a person from their essence, but should support their spiritual stability"³. Based on this, the experience of Japan is also relevant for Uzbekistan, which shows the need to harmonize culture and moral values along with technology in ensuring information security.

When considering foreign experience in the field of information security and its significance in the context of social philosophy, the issue manifests itself not only in the technical or legal sphere, but also as a global phenomenon related to the preservation of the conscious and spiritual stability of society. The development of information security policy in Western countries is closely related to the protection of human rights, the preservation of

¹ Westin A. Privacy and Freedom. – New York: Ig Publishing, 2003. – 246 b. – B. 87.

² Castells M. The Information Age: Economy, Society and Culture. – Oxford: Blackwell, 2000. – 606 b. – B. 71.

³ Nishitani K. Religion and Nothingness. – Tokyo: University of Tokyo Press, 1982. – 368 b. – B. 142.

personal data, and ensuring freedom of information. In the Swedish experience, the principle of openness, along with increasing transparency in the process of public administration, has strengthened citizens' trust in information. F. Fukuyama explains this process as "the most important element of social capital is trust, without which political and economic systems cannot be stable"⁴. Consequently, information security policy is not only a protection mechanism, but also a philosophical factor in the formation of social capital in society.

In the experience of the USA and the European Union, strategies for ensuring cyberspace security are more focused on legal norms, regulating information flows, and increasing citizens' responsibility. For example, in the "Cybersecurity Strategy" of the European Union, not only technological protection, but also the training of public consciousness, increasing the digital literacy of citizens are recognized as a separate area. J. Habermas interpreted this process as "communicative rational communication as a necessary condition for achieving consensus in society"⁵. Based on this, based on European experience, it can be said that information security serves to strengthen openness and harmony in society.

In the experience of Eastern countries, in particular South Korea and Singapore, it is observed that information security policy is effective through the harmonization of technological innovations with spiritual values. In these countries, information security is considered not only as a state policy, but also as an integral part of social culture. Z. Bauman notes that "information flows are the main sign of modernity, and the true protection of a person is embodied not in external mechanisms, but in his internal moral stability"⁶. Based on this point of view, it can be said that the experience of the East is also relevant for Uzbekistan, since technological means become more effective in combination with spiritual immunity.

When foreign experience in the field of information security and their significance are assessed in the context of social philosophy, they manifest themselves as a conceptual factor in the formation of modern human consciousness, strengthening spiritual immunity, and stabilizing society in the process of globalization. The experience of the USA, the European Union, Japan, and other countries shows that information security is directly related not only to technical protection, but also to protecting public consciousness from ideological manipulations, developing critical thinking in citizens, and protecting national values. As M. McLuhan noted, "media expands a person's sensory organs, therefore the perception of reality by society is formed through information systems"⁷. In this regard, foreign experience interprets information security as a socio-cultural process.

In the experience of the European Union, legal mechanisms such as the GDPR, along with the protection of personal data, ensure that citizens feel free in the information space. This, from the point of view of social philosophy, creates an atmosphere of trust and prepares the ground for stability in society. A. Giddens explains this situation by stating that "in the late modern era, the issue of security is closely connected with the strengthening of social trust"⁸.

⁴ Fukuyama F. Trust: The Social Virtues and the Creation of Prosperity. – New York: Free Press, 1995. – 457 b. – B. 26.

⁵ Habermas J. Moralbewußtsein und kommunikatives Handeln. – Frankfurt am Main: Suhrkamp, 1992. – 418 s. – S. 201.

⁶ Bauman Z. Liquid Modernity. – Cambridge: Polity Press, 2001. – 240 b. – B. 114.

⁷ McLuhan M. Understanding Media: The Extensions of Man. – New York: McGraw-Hill, 1964. – 359 p. – P. 22.

⁸ Giddens A. Modernity and Self-Identity. – Cambridge: Polity Press, 1991. – 256 p. – P. 39.

Consequently, information security policy is not only a protection mechanism, but also a concept that serves to strengthen public trust.

In the experience of Eastern countries, in particular Japan, information security policy is aimed not only at technological solutions, but also at the spiritual stability of society. K. Nishida emphasizes that "true freedom is formed by strengthening the inner world of a person, and technology should serve as a means to this process"⁹. This experience shows that strengthening moral immunity is an important component of information security.

When foreign experience in the field of information security and their significance are considered in the context of social philosophy, we see that they play a decisive role in strengthening the mental stability of humanity and the moral immunity of society. The experience of foreign countries shows that information security should not be limited to technical infrastructure, but should also be aimed at protecting public consciousness and cultural values. For example, in the experience of Germany, the "Federal Cybersecurity Strategy," along with the protection of information systems, also includes raising the legal awareness of citizens and protecting democratic values. In the words of M. Heidegger, "technology is not only a means, but also a force that determines a person's attitude towards being"¹⁰. This experience shows that strengthening moral immunity is an important component of information security.

When foreign experience in the field of information security and their significance are considered in the context of social philosophy, we see that they play a decisive role in strengthening the mental stability of humanity and the moral immunity of society. The experience of foreign countries shows that information security should not be limited to technical infrastructure, but should also be aimed at protecting public consciousness and cultural values. For example, in the experience of Germany, the "Federal Cybersecurity Strategy," along with the protection of information systems, also includes raising the legal awareness of citizens and protecting democratic values. In the words of M. Heidegger, "technology is not only a means, but also a force that determines a person's attitude towards being"¹¹. Thus, the experience of Japan is based on the development of moral immunity, in addition to technological control of information security.

The European Union's data protection policy (GDPR) harmonizes information security from a legal, philosophical, and social point of view. This system guarantees the inviolability of personal data and ensures the harmony of freedom and responsibility in the information space. A. Touraine emphasizes that this process is "determined by the ability of modern society to self-awareness through its information systems"¹². Thus, foreign experience, from the point of view of social philosophy, shows that information security policy ensures stability by strengthening public consciousness and moral immunity.

Foreign experience in the field of information security and their significance in the context of social philosophy are directly related to ensuring the existence, mental stability, and moral immunity of humanity in the digital age. Strategies developed in Western countries, in

⁹ Nishida K. Last Writings: Nothingness and the Religious Worldview. – Honolulu: University of Hawaii Press, 1990. – 180 p. – P. 118.

¹⁰ Heidegger M. Vremya i bytiye. – Moskva: Respublika, 1993. – 447 b. – B. 218.

¹¹ Nishitani K. Religion and Nothingness. – Tokyo: University of Tokyo Press, 1982. – 368 b. – B. 142.

¹² Touraine A. Un nouveau paradigme. – Paris: Fayard, 2007. – 300 p. – P. 203.

particular, the US "National Cybersecurity Strategy" and the UK "Cyber Essentials" programs, along with technological protection, are aimed at increasing the mental preparedness of citizens, and this approach serves to strengthen social stability. M. Castells notes that "in the information society, the hierarchy of power consists not in controlling information flows, but in managing the meaning given to them"¹³. In this sense, foreign experiences demonstrate that the effectiveness of information security also depends on the degree to which public consciousness possesses stability and critical thinking..

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¹³ Castells M. The Information Age: Economy, Society and Culture. – Oxford: Blackwell, 1998. – 594 b. – B. 376.